

Classroom Report

From Theory to Practice and Back Again: Mentorship, Apprenticeship, and Experiential Pre- Service Mathematics Teacher Education

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ABSTRACT: We provide an account of a unique pre-service teacher education experience: during the fall semester of the senior undergraduate year, the first author completed two Teaching Assistantships in undergraduate mathematics courses taught by the second and third authors. The first course was a ‘mathematics for liberal arts’ course called Mathematical Explorations, and the second course was a University Precalculus course. While the second and third authors share an orientation towards student-centered pedagogies such as active learning, the ways in which they enact these pedagogies in the classroom are different. This experience gave the first author (at the time a pre-service teacher, and now a licensed high school mathematics teacher in Massachusetts Public Schools) a unique chance to learn the pedagogies of two ‘active learning professors’ while becoming experienced with their enactments as well as discerning which influences of each the first author found important in her developing teacher identity; we see this as an exemplar of learning the theory-practice connection, which we stylize as a double entendre, also meaning the literal *practicing of* theory. The article underscores the necessary programmatic matters that would need to be considered to reproduce this dual Teaching Assistantship experience in other university departments dealing with mathematics teacher training and licensure, while also underscoring the importance of (1) the mentorship, (2) the apprenticeship, and (3) the experiential dimensions of pre-service mathematics teacher education.

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Introduction

Student-centered pedagogies such as inquiry-based learning occur in aesthetic contexts; “all inquiry is an art,” says Garrison (2010, pp. 87–88). Hence, if one is to avow such aesthetics, one must also admit—simultaneously—that “there is no deep distinction between theory and practice” (Garrison, 2010, p. 87). This deep non-distinction between theory and practice has critical consequences for teacher education. If teacher educators are to promote student-centered or progressivist pedagogies such as inquiry-based learning with their pre-service teachers, how is it possible to authentically mentor (viz. within the very formal structure of undergraduate degree programs) pre-service teachers to both understand and embody them? One clear answer is through educational *experience* (Dewey, 1938/2015), for it is in such practical, educative experiences that we come to *embody the theories* through which we wish to live our lives. However, this proposal is quite lofty to think of making concrete, because the literature has documented for decades the enormous gap between mathematics education research and the actual, lived labor of the practicing mathematics teacher. Eschewing the promotion of theory-practice experiences for pre-service teachers leads to their teaching of mathematics in the abstract and hence indicates the dangers of educational theory remaining only within the bounds of the collegiate intelligentsia and not with teachers in schools (Schneider et al., 2024). This is of great concern to us, the authors.

In the next section, we turn to Boyer’s (the first author) experience as a pre-service teacher and as a university student. Then, in the remaining sections, we describe our theoretical perspective, followed by an account of von Renesse’s (the third author) and Moore’s (the second author) classrooms where Boyer was a Teaching Assistant (TA) in both concurrently. We conclude with remarks about program structure that we believe to be necessary to consider when replicating the experiment reported in this text in other mathematics teacher licensure programs.

Stepping In: The Setting

I (Boyer, the first author) am a recently minted high school mathematics teacher in suburban New England in the US. I earned my degree from Westfield State University—a small, public, comprehensive state university that was originally founded as one of the first three teacher education colleges in the US. In the fall semester of my senior year of undergraduate studies, I served as a TA for two undergraduate mathematics courses—under the faculty supervision of the second and third authors, von Renesse and Moore—concurrent with my pre-practicum training. These courses were a ‘mathematics for liberal arts’ course and a Precalculus course.⁴ Immediately after these experiences, I began my Student Teaching (practicum) the following semester.

When we typically think of a TA, we think of a student who is capable and resourceful enough—perhaps remarkably so—that the professor trusts them to take over the control of their class. In this formulation, the TA’s main task is to ease the workload of the professor, so that the professor can focus on research or other classes. My experience was different. My TAs were centered around what I needed to work on as a pre-service teacher going into my practicum. For this reason, I considered myself a *Teaching* Assistant which I believe to be different from a *Teacher* Assistant.

⁴ A description of the courses is provided later in the article.

When I was making my schedule for the fall semester of my senior year, I needed six additional credits to meet graduation requirements. von Renesse, who was my advisor throughout my time at Westfield State, suggested I serve as a TA to fulfill my additional credits. The process for becoming a TA was quite easy. The first step was determining the courses of which I would like to be a part. I chose one course I was currently taking (a ‘mathematics for liberal arts’ course called Mathematical Explorations) that I loved, and a course (Precalculus) that I knew would fill in some conceptual mathematical gaps I had before going into my practicum. The second step was asking the professors if they would have me as a TA in their courses. Being my advisor, von Renesse agreed during our advising meeting. I had never had Moore before because at the time he was a new professor in our department, so I tracked him down one day to ask him if he would also have me as a TA in his course, and he agreed as well. The final step in this process was to fill out the paperwork to apply for two independent studies. There is no course offering at Westfield State to become a TA, so my professors had to each write a syllabus for an independent study, have it approved by the department chair, and finally the registrar's office. Firstly, the mathematics department at Westfield State is unique because each professor has a student-centered teaching style. Throughout my four years as part of this department, I never once sat through a lecture⁵ in any of my mathematics courses. For this approach to work for a future teacher, the department must have an intentional pedagogical orientation towards getting students involved in their own learning and invested in their own success as inquiry-based teachers. This unique experience is why von Renesse recommended that I finish my degree by being a TA; she knew that whomever my mentor was would give me the support I would need to teach using student-centered or inquiry-based pedagogies in my future classroom.

In addition to being a TA, I did pre-practicum placements in two different local high schools. The first of my 30 hours was at Springfield High School of Science and Technology in Springfield, Massachusetts. The second, which was done concurrently with my two TAs, was at Pioneer Valley Performing Arts School (PVPA) in South Hadley, Massachusetts. At PVPA I was placed with a teacher who was inspired by Peter Liljedahl's (2021) *Building Thinking Classrooms* (henceforth, BTC), which was a perfect fit because I had been trained to teach in this way in my Methods class. Because of this, it was easy for me to insert myself into the role of the teacher when I taught my lessons. A limitation was that I was only there once a week, and I only taught a total of two lessons. There was no time for me to be involved in the planning for the next time I would be there, and there was no time for me to get to know the students. Other than the two 40-minute classes I taught, I was just observing my cooperating teacher, which didn't help me to discover who I am as a teacher.

For the two Independent Studies at Westfield State, I served as a TA for two very different undergraduate mathematics courses. The first was an honors section of a ‘mathematics for liberal arts’ course called Mathematical Explorations. This course is a non-traditional mathematics class that, as the title suggests, asks students to explore mathematics. During the course, we focused on things that seemed to not be related to mathematics at all, and explored how they are related to mathematics in captivating ways. Units included origami, *salsa rueda* dancing, Islamic art, and games like Hex. In each unit students were asked to figure out the mathematical connection on their own, make conjectures and then prove why they work. This class was designed for students who think they aren't good at mathematics, or don't like mathematics. The intention was to get them to

⁵ By lecture, we mean a lesson structure whose primary task is the teacher, having prepared notes to guide one's thinking through a concept or topic *in a particular way*, stands at the front of the classroom and delivers a “speech” with these notes. This is different than facilitating a whole-class discussion, which we consider to be an active-learning element.

realize that mathematics can be exciting, and that it is more about *creating* and *deep thinking*—something that every student has the ability to do—than about memorizing procedures.⁶

The second class in which I served as TA was a Precalculus course. This was a traditional mathematics class where students were working with “traditional” mathematical concepts. During the course, we focused on several families of transcendental functions, and their structures. Units included trigonometric functions, exponential functions, logarithmic functions, the number e , logistic functions, limits and power functions, and polynomials. This class was designed for students who need it for their degree, and students going into the Calculus sequence. My professor for this class, Moore, talked to the other professors in our department who usually teach Calculus to find out what they see their students struggling with the most, and centered the class around those topics to ensure students are as well-prepared as they can be for Calculus I.

I had two major roles in both of my TA classes. The first included tasks that would be normally associated with a TA. For example, I would assess student work, which looked different in each class. In Mathematical Explorations, I was assessing student work as they were working on the boards in their small groups, and provided feedback in real time so they could adjust their thinking. In Precalculus, I was grading student problem sets with specific feedback for each student to revise their work. Once a week I would meet with each of my professors for about an hour to discuss the plan for the week. During these meetings I was giving input on what we would do in class, and often we would talk about students to make decisions about what they need in class. *I was also teaching full lessons in both classes, with regular occurrence.* This looked different in each class because of the setup of the two classes. In Mathematical Explorations, this included introducing tasks and facilitating whole class discussions. In Precalculus, this included short periods of direct instruction, and whole class and small group investigations of concepts. Finally, I was becoming comfortable in every setting in the classroom. This is something that Moore calls a *habitus*, which is being comfortable with discomfort.⁷ I was developing my habitus standing in front of a class and speaking, working with small groups, orchestrating whole class discussions, and helping one-on-one with individual students.

The second role was more important to me, and the main reason I wanted to be a TA instead of taking random classes to fill my remaining graduation credits: I was learning about myself as a teacher. My professors each practice slightly different pedagogies, and even though I was asked to write about my pedagogy in my education classes, I never felt like I actually believed what I was writing. The issue with pre-practicum is that there is little time to actually teach, and a lot of time to observe. So, if we learn by doing, I was learning a lot about how to be a great observer, and not as much about how to be a great teacher. Through my experiences in both of my TA classes, and learning the pedagogies of my professors, I was able to develop my own pedagogy—and *I actually believe in this one.*

In education there are theoretical perspectives that teachers take that contribute to their pedagogy. von Renesse practices a mix of the Problem Solving and Social Constructivism (Manizade et al., 2023). The Problem Solving perspective asks students to come to their own understanding of the mathematics concepts they are learning. This means that students are finding multiple solutions and thinking for themselves instead of a teacher telling them how they should

⁶ This phrasing comes from the syllabus for the Mathematical Explorations course being discussed in the present article; the syllabus and its wording were written by the second author, von Renesse.

⁷ Strictly speaking, *habitus* is a philosophical and sociological term that refers to the influence that culture and cultural knowledge has on a person's reactions or responses to the world. Moore uses this term to refer to one's arrival at a “comfortable” synthesis of one's background influences and one's pedagogical influences, with the result of “being a teacher” who is comfortable being uncomfortable with themselves, bringing forth all of their cultural background, in front of a classroom of students who are fundamentally different than they are.

understand the concept. The Social Constructivism perspective asks the learning to be a community effort. So rather than individuals having knowledge, the knowledge is a shared experience of the classroom community. The method that she uses to execute these perspectives is called Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL; Laursen & Rasmussen, 2019; von Renesse & Ecke, 2015). There are four major goals of IBL: for students to be engaged in meaningful mathematics, for students to be collaborating in their development of their understanding, for instructors to inquire into student thinking, and for instruction to be equitable and inclusive of rigorous mathematical learning, and mathematical identity-building. When Peter Liljedahl's (2021) BTC was published, von Renesse switched her language to align with his book because it was growing quickly in popularity. The book is a set of instructions on how to make your students think on their own about mathematics instead of mimicking what their teacher is telling them to do.

Moore practices the Structuralism perspective (Manizade et al., 2023) which asks students to see the whole structure of the mathematics they are learning. The easiest way to describe this perspective is with a metaphor Moore often uses when talking about Structuralism. If we are building a house, we first have to lay the foundation, then we can put up the frame, then the walls, then the roof. Decorations (e.g., special case results) come last. When it's all done, you can step back and ask your students if they can see a house. We can do the same thing with mathematics, and after laying out the structures, we can ask our students if they see it. Hopefully they can say 'yes.' Another aspect that is important to Structuralism is the saying, "we learn by speaking, and teach by listening" (e.g., Baldino & Cabral, 2024).⁸ If the teacher is standing in the front of the class lecturing, and students are taking notes, the teacher is the one who is learning because they are the one that's doing all the talking. Teachers need to shift this to make the students speak, and therefore learn, while the teacher *steps back and listens to what they have to say*.

My (Boyer's) own pedagogy is a mix of both pedagogies I experienced as a TA. I believe that students should be thinking and figuring things out for themselves. It is easier for a student to understand a concept if they are the ones developing that understanding. This is something that both my professors focused on in their classes. I also believe that everything in mathematics is connected—if my course in Complex Analysis taught me anything, it is that fact. Making students look for the structures behind the mathematics they are doing is important for them to make connections between mathematical ideas. I think this will benefit their understanding of mathematics as a whole, instead of viewing it as a bunch of pieces that do not fit together. In Structuralism, multiple representations are important. This is also something that's emphasized in the Problem Solving perspective when students are asked to find their own way of understanding. I like to use my students' solutions from their own problem solving as the multiple representations for which Structuralism asks. Finally, a central tenet of BTC is a technique called a Gallery Walk. This is when students will walk to their peers' board work, the students whose work is on display will explain their method, and their peers will ask questions or make connections to their own work. I would like to use this as a way for my students to learn by speaking, because they will be the ones explaining and questioning. My role will be to listen and offer support as needed. I believe that the Problem Solving, Social Constructivism, and Structuralism perspectives on teaching all fit very nicely together, and BTC is a great way to utilize and think about all of them.

I benefited a lot from my experiences as a TA. I chose a Precalculus class because I was not particularly confident with trigonometry thanks to taking it in high school during the COVID

⁸ This phrase is borrowed from the work of Roberto Baldino and Tânia Cabral in Brazil (e.g., Baldino & Cabral, 2024). While they do not explicitly say it is structuralist, Moore was trained by them and through his own research arrived at the conclusion that this phrase is structuralist in nature. This characterization also comports with Lacan's psychoanalysis (e.g., Lacan, 1991/2007), on whose theories Baldino, Cabral, and Moore base their work.

shutdown in 2020. Through the semester I was able to figure out why I didn't understand trigonometry, and work toward filling in my gaps. The way that Moore structured his trigonometry unit made me realize that I didn't previously understand trigonometry because I was taught all the *results* of the Unit Circle before *learning* the Unit Circle. After seeing where all those 'special' results come from in Moore's class I understood the underlying structures of trigonometry.

Through the TAs, I was also able to get more teaching experience before going into practicum. Before teaching for the first time in Precalculus, I had only taught two lessons in front of actual students. This was intimidating to me because during practicum I would be teaching a lot, and I felt that I wasn't prepared after only teaching a few times. Something that I did not have a lot of practice with before this semester was adjusting lessons based on student needs. We did this a lot in Mathematical Explorations because students were working at their own pace. So, we would plan to get through more than we did, talk about where the students got to, and develop a new plan for the next class based on what our students needed. Through all my experiences I got a chance to think about who I am as a teacher which was immensely helpful for me when I started my practicum. Having an idea of why I teach the way I do alleviated a lot of the stress that came with practicum.

My biggest question going into practicum was if students would respond well to my teaching style. During my TAs, I was working with college students, and these students are very different from high schoolers because they are choosing to go to school instead of school being mandatory for them to attend. I quickly noticed that my high schoolers were less likely to think independently about mathematics. They would ask for help right away, or wait for one of the teachers in the room to offer support before attempting the next part of the problem. Overall, they had been taught that if they wait they will receive help because my host teacher was always quick to step in. I also fell into this habit as I taught more.

I also quickly learned that the pre-written curriculum used at PVPA doesn't have problems that are interesting enough to produce multiple paths to the solution. They are very structured and walk the students through a very specific way of solving the problem. This made Gallery Walks very hard because everyone came to the answer in the same way. I also noticed that students were reluctant to look at another group's board or ask other students for help. The students believed that the teachers in the room were the only source of knowledge.

Something that did work well for me was getting my students to talk about mathematics. When I would insert myself into a group, I would always start by asking them to tell me what they were thinking. This made sure that the students were the ones learning because they were speaking and doing. One time I was walking around while students were developing a way to test if a point is on a parabola by using the Pythagorean Theorem, and I had a group that had just answered 'yes' to a point they were testing. I asked them if they could explain how they determined it was on the parabola, and they told me that it just 'looks like it is.' I knew that the point was on the parabola, but the point of the lesson was to develop a way to say with absolute certainty that a point *is* on a parabola. I told them that I thought it wasn't on the parabola, and that I was challenging them to prove me wrong. So, they did, and they were so excited to tell me I was wrong! If I hadn't gotten them to talk about what they were learning they wouldn't have gotten anything out of the lesson.

During practicum, my Calculus class was the most challenging. This was a class of mostly seniors who did not want my host teacher to use BTC methods of teaching. This class would refuse to sit in random groups, refused to work at the boards, and refused to think on their own. One day we got them to work at the boards instead of the tables by introducing a topic that involved a lot of drawing, and class went—according to the host teacher—'100 times better' than it usually did. PVPA is a performing arts school, so my students would take any opportunity they

got to draw. During this lesson, students who normally ‘check out’ and look at their phones were actively engaged in the work. Students who normally sit and do nothing were excited to be understanding the lesson. This experience solidified my belief in this style of teaching because the class did a full 180° flip in dynamics, and everyone benefited from it.

The biggest takeaway I had from practicum is to establish classroom norms and community as early as possible. I think my host teacher failed to do this in his Calculus class, and as a result he and his students struggled all year. The students need to feel like their teacher and peers are supporting them in order to be successful, and this will be my top priority going into my first year of teaching.

Being a Teaching Assistant was the best thing I could have done to finish my degree. I learned so much that I will be using in my future classroom. My confidence in myself as a teacher has improved, and my future high school students will benefit from my TA experiences in Mathematical Explorations and Precalculus. I will forever be grateful for this opportunity and will recommend it to every pre-service teacher I meet.

Stepping Back Out: The Role of Mentorship, Apprenticeship, and Induction to the Profession

Literature on the important effects of mentorship and induction are well documented. For example, in a widely cited study, Ingersoll and Strong (2011) performed a systematic review and found that, overall, these initiatives for newly minted teachers provide significant impacts on teacher retention (staying in the field for a long time) and on teachers’ instructional practices, the latter of which, in turn, leads to improved student achievement on a broad range of assessment measures. They identified several themes in the literature that mentorship and induction positively impact: “keeping students on task, using effective student questioning practices, adjusting classroom activities to meet students’ interests, maintaining a positive classroom atmosphere, and demonstrating successful classroom management” (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011, p. 201). However, they also found that when these measures are conducted in urban, poor schools, notwithstanding the positive student impacts they have, they nonetheless did not lead to improvements in teacher *retention*; this is to be expected, however, for political reasons that are quite apparent as we write this paper in 2025.

In the dual-TA experience of the present account, we add the dimension of *apprenticeship* to the mentorship and induction framework. For us, the role of apprenticeship mirrors the pedagogies the second and third authors employ in their courses; we describe these pedagogies in two subsequent sections of the present text. Apprenticeship, for us, brings the professor–candidate relationship into a less hierarchical format, balancing the authority roles. In this perspective, the candidate is treated as a colleague rather than a trainee, and—just as the first author described above—the professor ‘sits back and listens to what the [teacher candidate] has to say,’ while the candidate does the same with respect to the professor. In this way, our apprenticeship model is dialogical and relational in nature, which we believe contributes to the radicality of the import of this text.

The Role of the Theory-Practice Connection

With Manizade and Beswick, Moore (the second author) found that among Western approaches to mathematics education, there were several widely avowed epistemological perspectives to the teaching of mathematics (Manizade et al., 2023); in this framework, it is avowed that “theory drives teaching practice” (p. 92) and, most notably, that

Teachers' subjective decision-making is based on [professional knowledge, competencies, skills, and beliefs] that they possess, and the configuration of [these] elements “stabilizes [the teacher’s] world” (Žižek, 2012, p. 367) through their subjective, decision-making process. (Manizade et al., 2023, p. 92)

While this is a bit of an unconventional way to conceive of the relationship between beliefs and actions, we find it to be compelling nonetheless, chiefly because a “[teacher’s] decision-making process produces observable [pedagogical actions]” (Manizade et al., 2023, p. 92). In other words, we take the position that teachers' knowledge about theory is a precondition for their real decision-making about pedagogy. In the context of the experience we describe presently, this manifests in the way in which we (von Renesse and Moore) discussed pedagogy at length with Boyer each week, making explicit the ways in which we were thinking about our own decision-making apropos of our theoretical perspectives on teaching. We would, for example, demonstrate the way we would carry out a particular teaching task, and then discuss with Boyer how we made sense of the decisions we made, after which she would try out ‘her own version’ of our pedagogical actions. Neither of us believe in ‘perfect teaching,’ nor that ‘our ways are the best ways,’ so our goal for Boyer was to be able to ‘try walking in our shoes’ and then, through her own self-reflection, decide how she desired to attempt to accomplish the same pedagogical goal. This sometimes resulted in Boyer’s interventions being edited versions of ours. As a result, and as is documented above, she was able to finish the dual-TA experience with a ‘realized intentionality’ towards her own future classroom. In this way, we see the experience we account presently as being *an exemplar of experiential theory-practice pedagogical education*.

The Classrooms

In this section, we (Moore and von Renesse) describe our classrooms individually, in order to explain some of the differences in the way we enact ‘active learning’ pedagogy. One key difference to note is that Moore’s marker of success for the lesson is that all students rise up to ‘the level of the floor,’ whereas von Renesse is less concerned with the homogeneity of students’ achievement and rather pushes each student to ‘keep climbing’ as much as they can, heading towards the ‘ceiling.’

von Renesse’s Classroom

I (von Renesse) use different techniques to group my students, sometimes using cards to randomize, sometimes chosen by me based on observation and student feedback. Having groups of students that work well together is crucial for my classes and many dimensions influence the creation of groups: working speed, prior knowledge, work ethic, attendance issues, friendships, language preferences, minoritized populations, etc. My primary goal is for students to be actively thinking about mathematics for as much time as possible. To that effort, I pretty much never lecture, but ask groups to work on tasks that are difficult enough to allow for different problem-solving approaches while discovering a bigger idea in mathematics, e.g., the definition of the derivative. If possible, I ask students to work on vertical, non-permanent surfaces to allow for knowledge mobility and constant engagement. Not all groups will be able to solve all problems in the given time, and some groups will work through interesting extension problems, but this is expected as students work at different speeds using different base knowledge. Depending on the progress of the groups, I facilitate gallery walks or short whole class discussions, these help students ask questions and connect the new ideas. Our new discovery can then be recorded as the big idea of this class session: this could be a definition, a theorem, a proof or explanation, or an

applied problem that was solved. Written assignments are used to summarize, explain in more detail and ground the new knowledge.

Moore's Classroom

While my (Moore's) content goals are structuralist⁹ (Manizade et al., 2023) in nature, my pedagogy draws primarily on the Solidarity Assimilation Methodology (SAM; Cabral et al., 2019), where two main cornerstones are permanent small groups of 3-4 students, and the conflation of "effort-based with content-based promotional criteria" (Cabral et al., 2019, p. 4). These permanent small 'solidarity' groups begin forming via the social link on the first day of class, where students who happen to find themselves at the same table get to know each other, including their emotional relationship with mathematics, their anxieties (about anything), and their dreams and hopes for the future (Baldino & Cabral, 2008; Skovsmose, 2014). Students in my courses work in the same small group all semester; sometimes a student will change groups organically for reasons that usually relate to their peers' attendance habits. I lecture as little as possible, and my decision to lecture is determined by the course's student population (e.g., what year, either majors or non-majors, what the purpose of the course is within a larger degree program), and the content of the course. For some extreme examples, I lecture approximately 50% of the time in an introductory statistics course for non-majors and approximately 5% of the time in an upper-division, required mathematics education course.

In the Precalculus course Boyer co-taught with me, I estimate that I lectured about 20% of the time. These lectures serve the primary goal of introducing students to the symbols and words (and what I *mean* when I use them) germane to the content topic. After establishing the 'rules of language' for the day's topic, students then begin working on assigned problems together in their solidarity groups. I present the assigned problems as a set that students typically work on for 2-3 class periods. I do very little telling during this period of time; the students work together, trying to make sense of the problems on their own, working with their solidarity groups either on the room's wraparound blackboards or on an application such as GeoGebra, and oftentimes, students must do both at the same time in order to solve the problems I have assigned. Once a set of problems is done, I collect and read them, leaving detailed editorial marks about mistakes, but I read solutions as 'texts' meaning that I read each group's solution start to finish, without pre-judging their approach. If they have a valid approach, even if it's different than my own, I laud them for their effort. This leads my students to teach me something new about mathematics each semester, without fail. Crucially, I do not *grade* my students' work during the semester.¹⁰ I return each problem set to students, with my editorial marks, and they have the option to revise them into a second draft or third draft *ad nauseum*. The point of this is that at the end of the semester, I collect their portfolios (binders with all collected, revised problem sets, along with reflective somatic journals from each class session), and then read each student's portfolio as a 'text' from start to finish, evaluating it on its completeness and correctness. By leaving the 'concrete grades' out of the picture until the end of the semester, I sustain my students' Lack in the Other (Cabral et al., 2019). My grading schemes are generally around these percentages: 10% disposition towards the solidarity group, 30% attendance with only two absences allowed for the semester, and 60% portfolio correctness and completion. This grading scheme illustrates that the two primary goals I

⁹ The epistemological assumptions of structuralism follow the structure of language in that in order to write poetry, one must first understand metonymic grammar. This is what Lacan (e.g., 1977) called the quilting of language. This perspective also avows the role of manipulatives and multiple representations, such as using actual power tools to build things out of wood rather than, e.g., merely reading books about woodworking.

¹⁰ In Moore's class, Madison conducted a significant amount of this grading/reading/commenting on student's work. Both Moore and von Renesse have similar grading philosophies, usually referred to as *un-grading* or *contract-based labor*.

have for my students are (1) daily attendance and involvement with the solidarity group, and (2) work/effort is privileged over correctness, although, in the end, the students who attend every day and earnestly work with their groups overwhelmingly end up passing my courses. It is not unusual for me to hear that solidarity groups have turned into longstanding friendships outside of my courses.

Necessary Considerations and Final Words

In this section, we conclude with what we believe to be necessary considerations to help interested practitioners decide if they can and/or want to create similar experiences in their department. Our department offers four courses that are specifically designed to support future mathematics teachers: Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching I and II, Technology and Mathematics, and Foundations of Teaching Mathematics (Pre-Practicum), all taught in the mathematics department. While students learn the basics of the theory of mathematics education in these classes, they also experience many flavors of active learning in our department. This mix of theory and practice helps our students be ready to be a TA in their senior year so they can work on specific techniques like facilitating discussions, asking good questions, etc. We noticed that the pre-practicum experiences in middle and high schools that our program includes often have students in the *observation role* and may not leave students with enough practical experience. Their practicum semester, on the other hand, is often overwhelming since the future teacher needs to be ready for anything. Being a TA is a perfect bridge to practicum.

To pair a future teacher with a faculty member, we find it crucial to know what their classroom and pedagogy look like. Visiting each other's classes to see teaching in action is an important tool to do so, but it has to be clear that the purpose of a visit is to learn from each other, not to judge each other. Once you have a good sense of which learning experiences each colleague has to offer, we can ask what our future teacher is ready to learn next, both pedagogically and in terms of content.

I (Boyer, the first author) believe that great professors create great teachers—professors who are willing to let their students see into their worlds further than the traditional teacher preparation classes that everyone takes; professors who are so passionate about creating great teachers that they teach in a more difficult way to make sure that their students are getting the most out of their classes. Lecturing is easy but letting your students take the wheel and tell you what they know is more rewarding.¹¹ This is the way the professors in the mathematics department at Westfield State University operate, and one of the reasons that this apprenticeship worked so well.

I also believe that future great teachers must have a burning desire to be great teachers. We must want it more than anything and work harder for it than we have ever worked for anything in our lives. It was with this way of thinking that I went through not only my TA classes, but my entire bachelor's degree program, and the way I plan to move forward with my master's degree. For a teacher candidate to succeed in this apprenticeship model, they must show a great desire to be a great teacher.

¹¹ For a comprehensive resource on inquiry-based learning in Liberal Arts Mathematics, the reader is encouraged to read the open-access *Discovering the Art of Mathematics* book series and accompanying resources at www.artofmathematics.org.

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